

Libero.it Password Leak - An Analysis In-Depth

Rocco Gagliardi

Defense Department, scip AG
roga@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Marc Ruef (Editor)

Research Department, scip AG
maru@scip.ch
<https://www.scip.ch>

Abstract: The password leak of LiberoMail provides a solid data-set to analyze password behavior of users. Womens passwords tend to be more secure. Users born in the 90s use safer passwords. Always use dual-factor authentication to be protected from such leaks.

Keywords: Age, Complexity, Cybersecurity, Gender, Italy, Joke, Leak, LiberoMail, Mail, North

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2018 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180913> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

One evening, during my holidays in Italy, with a couple of friends we joked about how passwords are used that protect many aspects of our electronic life. Since we were from different villages, we started to joke about possible password variations related to the territory. Meanwhile, between a drink and the other, I wondered if I could analyze the passwords with other parameters, such as gender, age, address.

3. The Libero.it leak

In 2016, the Italian email hosting service *LiberoMail* revealed an attack resulting in exfiltration of many database records. Not well implemented security measures exposed user and passwords in clear text along with the address and some other user's details. *The LiberoMail users database was breached* [1].

I decided to take a look at the data, clean them up (in addition to the security problem, they also had a data normalization problem), put everything in a database and run some queries on it.

4. The Data-set

The data set consists of approx. 700,000 records, not all with complete fields. In many cases, for example, the age has been extrapolated from the user name, from the e-mail address or even from the password itself.

4.1. Some simple counts

Measure	Value
Total records	700,517
Records without passwords	33,332
Records without information	97,569
Italian users	696,023
Other users	4,994

4.2. Gender and Age

The gender (declared by user) and the age distribution are reported in the next charts:

Figure: Breakdown of Gender and Age

5. The Analysis

Using our self-developed tools, we cleaned and normalized the raw-data and put the results in a relational DB.

For the analysis, we identified following characteristics:

5.1. Password

- **Length:** How many chars has the password
- **Complexity:** We add one point for each lowercase-, uppercase-, number-, punctuation-category, if present in the password
- **Common names:** Based on a list of most used Italian first and last names, we check if the names are part of the password

- Self-contained: We checked if the password contains the username (or part of it) or birthday (or part of it)

5.2. User

- Age: Sometime declared by user, sometime extrapolated from the username or password
- Region: The four Italian main regions (Nord, Center, South, Islands)

6. The Results

6.1. Password Length

Following charts shows how the password length *varies* [2] if compared with *gender* [3], age, and region.

Figure: Password length by gender

Figure: Password length by age

Figure: Password length by region

Remarks:

- Women uses longer passwords
- Age group 20-29 use longer passwords
- Password length of 7 and 8 chars are the most used
- The region does not influence the password length

6.2. Password complexity

Following charts shows how the password complexity varies if compared with gender, age, and region (one point for each lowercase-, uppercase-, number-, punctuation-category).

Figure: Password complexity by gender

Figure: Password complexity by age

Figure: Password complexity by region

Remarks:

- Women uses complex passwords
- Age group 20-29 use complex passwords
- The region does not influence the password complexity

6.3. Password Complexity vs Length

Following chart shows how the password length and complexity are related.

Figure: Password complexity by length

Remarks:

- 25% of 6-chars passwords have complexity 1
- Most of the passwords longer than 10-chars have also complexity 4

6.4. Usage of Common Names

Following chart shows how the user makes use of common names (most Italian used first and last names), aggregated by gender and region.

Figure: Usage of common names in passwords

Remarks:

- Women prefer common names in passwords
- Especially the women in northern Italy

6.5. Special Passwords

Following charts shows how the female and male users uses the specific passwords `juventus`, `napoli`, `amoremio`, `123456`.

Figure: Female usage of special passwords, by region

Figure: Male usage of special passwords, by region

Remarks:

- Users from Islands do not like password `123456`
- `juventus` and `napoli` are well divided by North/South

6.6. Top Passwords

Following charts shows the top 20 passwords and the top 20 passwords containing a common name.

Figure: Top passwords

Figure: Top passwords containing common names

Remarks:

- `popopo90` is the phonetic transcription of the stadium anthem of the Football World Championship Italia 90

7. Conclusion

Women seem to have safer passwords than men, even if in the north they exaggerate with the use of common names. Nice as usual the diatribes between Juventus and Napoli that remind us how in Italy football is always a protagonist.

The conclusion is to use at least dual-factor authentication for any of your accounts containing sensitive data. That means for every account.

8. External Links

- [1] <https://www.andreafortuna.org/cybersecurity/the-liberomail-users-database-was-breached/>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20110217>
- [3] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20091120>